

Maximum conversion in presence of inert gas

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In the case of equilibrium reactions in gaseous phase or solid-gas phases, that takes place in the presence of inert gas and under isothermal-isobaric or isothermal-isochoric conditions, the conversion is maximum, if reactants are stoichiometrically mixed and the amount of inert gas is constant.

A particular case is represented by the oxidation reactions with air, in which nitrogen is the inert gas,

and certain reactions in which it is both inert gas and product,

We took into consideration a number of 20 oxidation reactions with air, many of them having practical importance. Calculations made by using Lagrange's method of undetermined multipliers, when reactions take place under isothermal-isobaric or isothermal-isochoric conditions, point out that, for high values of equilibrium constants ($K_x \rightarrow \infty, K_c \rightarrow \infty$), the conversion is maximum in case of stoichiometric mixture. On the other hand, for medium and low values of the equilibrium constants, conversion is maximum if the added amount of air is less than the amount corresponding to a stoichiometric mixture.

In case of chemical reactions, the equilibrium conversion (ξ) depends on the conditions of temperature and pressure in which the reaction takes place, the mixing proportion of reactants, and the presence of inert gas. In industrial and laboratory practical training scale, most reactions develop in isothermal-isobaric conditions. Few reactions take place at constant T, V . In these conditions, the equilibrium conversion depends only on the mixing proportion of reactants and the presence of inert gas. It was pointed out that in case of isothermal-isochoric reactions, in absence of inert gas, the conversion is maximum if the reactants are mixed stoichiometrically¹.

In this paper, we have analyzed the influence of inert gas and the mixing proportion on conversion (ξ) when reactions take place in isothermal-isobaric or isothermal-isochoric conditions. We also took into account oxidation reactions with air, when nitrogen was an inert gas.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometric mixture :

We will take into consideration the general equilibrium reaction in gaseous phase,

that takes place in the presence of inert gas, where I_n is inert

gas, n_{in} represents the amount of inert gas, R_1, \dots, R_j are reactants, P_{j+1}, \dots, P_c represent products and ν_1, \dots, ν_c are stoichiometric coefficients. There is a number of $c+1$ components participating in the reaction.

At the beginning of the reaction, the conversion $\xi = 0$ and the amount of products is zero; the amounts of reactants $n_1^0, n_2^0, \dots, n_j^0$ are variable and the amount of inert gas n_{in} is also variable, with the imposed condition that

$$n_1^0 + n_2^0 + \dots + n_j^0 + n_{\text{in}} = n^0 = \text{constant} \quad (2)$$

We aim to establish the proportion in which reactants should be mixed, in presence of inert gas, so that the value of equilibrium conversion ξ should be maximum, when the reaction takes place at constant T, p and the gaseous phase presents an ideal behavior.

For a certain value ξ of the equilibrium conversion, the amount of each of the c components is :

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} n_1 = n_1^0 - \nu_1 \xi; \\ \vdots \\ n_j = n_j^0 - \nu_j \xi; \\ n_{j+1} = \nu_{j+1} \xi \\ \vdots \\ n_c = \nu_c \xi \end{array} \right\} \quad (3)$$

and the total quantity of substance existing in the system is

$$n = \sum_{i=1}^{i=c} n_i + n_{in} = n^0 + \xi \Delta n \quad (4)$$

where Δn represents the change of gas amount that accompanies the reaction,

$$\Delta n = \sum_{i=j+1}^{i=c} \nu_i - \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \quad (5)$$

At equilibrium, the mole fractions corresponding to the components are

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} x_1 = \frac{n_1^0 - \nu_1 \xi}{n^0 + \xi \Delta n}; \\ \vdots \\ x_j = \frac{n_j^0 - \nu_j \xi}{n^0 + \xi \Delta n}; \\ x_{j+1} = \frac{\nu_{j+1} \xi}{n^0 + \xi \Delta n} \\ \vdots \\ x_c = \frac{\nu_c \xi}{n^0 + \xi \Delta n} \end{array} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The equilibrium constant $K_x(T, p)$ is written as

$$K_x = \frac{x_{j+1}^{\nu_{j+1}} \dots x_c^{\nu_c}}{x_1^{\nu_1} \cdot x_2^{\nu_2} \dots x_j^{\nu_j}} \quad (7)$$

and after replacing the mole fractions from eqn. (6),

$$K_x = \frac{(\nu_{j+1} \xi)^{\nu_{j+1}} \dots (\nu_c \xi)^{\nu_c}}{(n_1^0 - \nu_1 \xi)^{\nu_1} (n_2^0 - \nu_2 \xi)^{\nu_2} \dots (n_j^0 - \nu_j \xi)^{\nu_j} (n^0 + \xi \Delta n)^{\Delta n}} \quad (8)$$

By applying the logarithm, we obtain,

$$\ln K_x = \sum_{i=j+1}^{i=c} \nu_i \ln(\nu_i \xi) - \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \ln(n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi) - \Delta n \ln(n^0 + \xi \Delta n) \quad (9)$$

In the relation above, $n^0 = \text{constant}$, $\Delta n = \text{constant}$ and in isothermal-isobaric conditions $K_x = \text{constant}$. The equilibrium conversion ξ depends on the proportion by which the reactants are mixed. Thus, by differentiating at constant T and p , we obtain,

$$\sum_{i=j+1}^{i=c} \nu_i \frac{d\xi}{\xi} - \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \frac{dn_i^0}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi} + \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \frac{\nu_i d\xi}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi} - \Delta n \frac{\Delta n d\xi}{n^0 + \xi \Delta n} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Because ξ is maximum, it results that $d\xi = 0$, and eqn. (10) becomes

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \frac{\nu_i}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi_{\max}} dn_i^0 = 0 \quad (11)$$

By differentiating eqn. (2), it results,

$$dn_1^0 + dn_2^0 + \dots + dn_j^0 + dn_{in} = 0 \quad (12)$$

The last two relations must be satisfied simultaneously. By applying Lagrange's method of undetermined multipliers², we can write,

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \frac{\nu_i}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi_{\max}} dn_i^0 + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} dn_i^0 + \lambda dn_{in} = 0 \quad (13)$$

where λ is an undetermined multiplier.

As $dn_i^0 \neq 0$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, j$) and $\lambda \neq 0$, it results that a number of j conditions are satisfied simultaneously,

$$\frac{\nu_i}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi_{\max}} + \lambda = 0; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, j \quad (14)$$

to which another condition is added,

$$dn_{in} = 0; \quad n_{in} = \text{constant} \quad (15)$$

For the value of equilibrium conversion ξ to be maximum, it is necessary that, in eqn. (2), the amount of inert gas should be constant.

Relations (14) may also be written as

$$\frac{n_i^0}{\nu_i} = \xi_{\max} - \frac{1}{\lambda}; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, j \quad (16)$$

or

$$\frac{n_1^0}{\nu_1} = \frac{n_2^0}{\nu_2} = \dots = \frac{n_j^0}{\nu_j} = \frac{n_1^0 + n_2^0 + \dots + n_j^0}{\nu_1 + \nu_2 + \dots + \nu_j} = \frac{n^0 - n_{in}}{\nu_1 + \nu_2 + \dots + \nu_j} \quad (17)$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_1^0 &= \frac{\nu_1}{\nu_1 + \nu_2 + \dots + \nu_j} (n^0 - n_{in}) \\
 n_2^0 &= \frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1 + \nu_2 + \dots + \nu_j} (n^0 - n_{in}) \\
 &\vdots \\
 n_j^0 &= \frac{\nu_j}{\nu_1 + \nu_2 + \dots + \nu_j} (n^0 - n_{in}) \\
 n_{j+1}^0 &= 0 \\
 &\vdots \\
 n_c^0 &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

It results that, for any chemical reaction that takes place in isothermal-isobaric conditions in presence of inert gas, the equilibrium conversion ξ is maximum, if the reactants mix stoichiometrically and the amount of inert gas is constant. This conclusion also remains valid in the situation when the reaction takes place in absence of inert gas, when $n_{in} = 0$. The same result will be obtained if, by replacing the equilibrium constant $K_x(T, p)$, we should use the equilibrium constants $K_p(T)$ or $K_c(T)$, expressed by partial pressures, respectively by molar concentrations.

When solid substances participate in the reaction, their concentrations do not appear in the expressions of the equilibrium constants, and do not influence on the conversion. This is the reason why solid substances may be introduced in any amount in case of equilibrium reactions involving gas-solid phases.

The curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 1, with generated data, express the variation of conversion ξ as a function of the initial amount of nitrogen, $n_{N_2}^0$, for the ammonia synthesis reaction that takes place at constant T, p . For all curves, the position of the maximum corresponds to the stoichiometric mixture of the reactants. In case of reactions with decreasing volume ($\Delta n < 0, \Delta V < 0$), the presence of inert gas diminishes the value of conversion. On the contrary, in case of reactions with increasing volume ($\Delta n > 0, \Delta V > 0$), the situation is opposite, and in case of reactions with no change of volume ($\Delta n = 0, \Delta V = 0$) the conversion is the same and it does not matter if inert gas is present or absent. As the

Fig. 1. Equilibrium conversion ξ as a function of the initial amount of nitrogen ($n_{N_2}^0$) for the ammonia synthesis reaction, $N_2 + 3 H_2 \leftrightarrow 2 NH_3$, when $n_{N_2}^0 + n_{H_2}^0 = 4$ mol : (1) $K_x = 1, n_{in} = 1$ mol, (2) $K_x = 1, n_{in} = 0$ mol, (3) $K_c/V^2 = 16$ mol⁻².

equilibrium constant K_x increases, the maximum conversion ξ_{max} has higher values.

If reaction (1) takes place at constant T, V , it is more convenient to use the equilibrium constant $K_c(T)$,

$$K_c = \frac{(\nu_{j+1}\xi)^{\nu_{j+1}} \dots (\nu_c\xi)^{\nu_c}}{V^{\Delta n} (n_1^0 - \nu_1\xi)^{\nu_1} (n_2^0 - \nu_2\xi)^{\nu_2} \dots (n_j^0 - \nu_j\xi)^{\nu_j}} \tag{19}$$

where V represents the volume of the reaction system. By applying the logarithm to this relation, it results,

$$\ln K_c + \Delta n \ln V =$$

$$\sum_{i=j+1}^{i=c} \nu_i \ln (\nu_i \xi) - \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \ln (n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi) \tag{20}$$

Under isothermal-isochoric conditions, V, K_c and Δn are constants and by differentiating eqn. (20), it results,

$$\sum_{i=j+1}^{i=c} \nu_i \frac{d\xi}{\xi} - \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \frac{dn_i^0}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi} + \sum_{i=1}^{i=j} \nu_i \frac{\nu_i d\xi}{n_i^0 - \nu_i \xi} = \tag{21}$$

By imposing the condition that $\xi = \text{maximum}$ and $d\xi = 0$, we obtain the same eqn. (11) and the following calculations and results are identical.

As a conclusion, in case of isothermal-isochoric reactions that take place in the presence/absence of inert gas, it is necessary that the reactants should be mixed stoichiometrically and the amount of inert gas should be constant, $n_{in} = \text{constant}$, in order that the conversion of the reactants into products should be maximum. This result can easily be interpreted by taking into account the fact that, in case of reactions taking place at constant T, V , the value of conversion ξ is not affected by the presence of inert gas, independently if reactions take place with or without volume change (Fig. 1, curve 3). As the quantity K_c/V^2 increases, the value of maximum conversion rises accordingly.

Thus, we come to the conclusion that the stoichiometric mixture of reactants assures a maximum conversion in case of isothermal-isobaric (or isothermal-isochoric) reactions, independent of the values of T and p (or T and V) parameters at which the reaction takes place.

Non-stoichiometric mixture. Oxidation reactions with air :

In the case of oxidation reactions with air, nitrogen is an inert gas and it exists in the system but does not react with any of the substances participating at reaction,

In the case of certain oxidation reactions, nitrogen is both an inert gas and a product of reaction,

Our aim is to establish the proportion in which reactants and air should be mixed so that the value of equilibrium conversion ξ should be the maximum when the reaction takes place in isothermal-isobaric or isothermal-isochoric conditions. As oxygen is one of the reactants, the amount of O_2 involved in the reaction is variable; this is the reason why the amount of inert gas (N_2) will also be variable, with the condition that the molar ratio $\text{N}_2/\text{O}_2 = 4$.

In this case, calculations can not be made on the basis of a general reaction (1). Therefore, we will take into account some reactions of practical importance that take place in gaseous phase.

Reactions where nitrogen is only inert gas :

Among these, the following reactions are of greater importance :

The initial quantities of the reactants are written below the

reactions. These quantities are variable, under the imposed condition that

$$n_1^0 + 5 n_2^0 = n^0 = \text{constant} \quad (24)$$

In the case of these reactions as well as in the case of the following ones, the initial amount of reactants n^0 equals to the sum of the stoichiometric coefficients of the reactants, implying values of conversion situated within the interval $0 < \xi < 1$ and values of equilibrium constants between zero and infinity. For the reactions (22) and (23), $n^0 = 7 \text{ mol}$.

Fig. 2. Equilibrium conversion ξ as a function of the initial amount (n_{NO}^0) in case of the reaction (23), for various values of the equilibrium constant K_x .

Considering that these reactions take place in isothermal-isobaric conditions and proceeding in the same manner as in the case of the general reaction (1), it results,

$$K_x = \frac{4\xi^2(n^0 - \xi)}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2(n_2^0 - \xi)} \quad (25)$$

By applying the logarithm to eqn. (25) and then differentiating the result with the imposed conditions that $K_x = \text{constant}$, $\xi = \text{maximum}$, $d\xi = 0$, we obtain,

$$2 \frac{dn_1^0}{n_1^0 - 2\xi_{\text{max}}} + \frac{dn_2^0}{n_2^0 - \xi_{\text{max}}} = 0 \quad (26)$$

By differentiating eqn. (24), it results,

$$dn_1^0 + 5 dn_2^0 = 0 \quad (27)$$

Eqns. (26) and (27) must be satisfied simultaneously. By applying Lagrange's method of undetermined multipliers, we obtain a relation involving the quantities n_1^0 , n_2^0 and the maximum conversion, ξ_{\max} ,

$$10n_2^0 - n_1^0 = 8 \xi_{\max} \quad (28)$$

From eqns. (24) and (28), we finally obtain,

$$\xi_{\max} = (2n^0 - 3n_1^0)/8 \quad (29)$$

Consequently, it results that the maximum value of conversion (ξ_{\max}) decreases linearly with the amount of reactant n_1^0 , as shown in Fig. 2. Data presented in Table 1 show that ξ_{\max} decreases linearly with the amount of reactant n_1^0 , in

the case of all oxidation reactions where nitrogen is only inert gas. If we express ξ_{\max} by the initial amount of oxygen, n_2^0 , we also obtain a linear dependence,

$$\xi_{\max} = (15 n_2^0 - n^0)/8 \quad (30)$$

This time, ξ_{\max} increases linearly with the amount of oxygen, n_2^0 . By eliminating n_2^0 , from eqns. (24) and (25), we obtain,

$$K_x = \frac{20 \xi^2 (n^0 - \xi)}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2 (n^0 - n_1^0 - 5 \xi)} \quad (31)$$

Eqn. (31), where $n^0 = 7$ mol, allows the calculation of the equilibrium conversion ξ for various values of the amount of reactant n_1^0 , if the constant of equilibrium K_x has a particular value. Going on this manner, we obtain the curves of maximum (Fig. 2) where the points of maximum are situ-

Table 1. Oxidation reactions with air, in gaseous phase, where nitrogen is only inert gas

Sl. no.	Reaction, initial quantities of reactants n_1^0, n_2^0, \dots and expressions of the equilibrium constants K_x and K_c	Δn mol	Relations between initial quantities of reactants in order to obtain curves of maximum $\xi = f(n_1^0)$ similar to those presented in Fig. 2
Reaction with $\Delta n < 0$			
1.	$2N_2O + 3O_2 + 12N_2 \leftrightarrow 4NO_2 + 12N_2$ $n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$ $K_x = \frac{4^4 \xi^4 (n^0 - \xi)}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2 (n_2^0 - 3\xi)^3}$ $K_c = \frac{4^4 \xi^4 V}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2 (n_2^0 - 3\xi)^3}$	-1	$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 17$ mol $\xi_{\max} = (2n^0 - 5n_1^0)/24$ $0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{34}{5} > n_1^0 > 2$ $0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < K_c/V < \infty$
2.	$N_2O_3 + O_2 + 4N_2 \leftrightarrow N_2O_5 + 4N_2$ $n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$ $K_x = \frac{\xi(n^0 - \xi)}{(n_1^0 - \xi)(n_2^0 - \xi)}$ $K_c = \frac{\xi V}{(n_1^0 - \xi)(n_2^0 - \xi)}$	-1	$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 6$ mol $\xi_{\max} = (n^0 - 2n_1^0)/4$ $0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; 3 > n_1^0 > 1$ $0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < K_c/V < \infty$
3.	$2H_2C=CH_2 + O_2 + 4N_2 \leftrightarrow 2H_2C \begin{array}{c} \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \quad \quad O \end{array} CH_2 + 4N_2$ $n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$ $K_x = \frac{4\xi^2 (n^0 - \xi)}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2 (n_2^0 - \xi)}$ $K_c = \frac{4\xi^2 V}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2 (n_2^0 - \xi)}$	-1	$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 7$ mol $\xi_{\max} = (2n^0 - 3n_1^0)/8$ $0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{14}{3} > n_1^0 > 2$ $0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < K_c/V < \infty$
4.	$2C_6H_6 + 9O_2 + 36N_2 \leftrightarrow 2C_4H_2O_3 + 4CO_2 + 4H_2O + 36N_2$ $n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$ (C ₄ H ₂ O ₃ - maleic anhydride)	-1	$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 47$ mol $\xi_{\max} = (2n^0 - 11n_1^0)/72$

					$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{38}{7} > n_1^0 > 2$
					$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < VK_c < \infty$
11.	$2C_2H_6 + 4NH_3 + 5O_2 + 20N_2 \leftrightarrow 4HCN + 10H_2O + 20N_2$	3		$n_1^0 + n_2^0 + 5n_3^0 = n^0 = 31 \text{ mol}$	
	$n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad n_3^0 \quad 4n_3^0$			$n_1^0 = \frac{1}{2} n_2^0$	
				$\xi_{\max} = (2n^0 - 11n_1^0)/40$	
				$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{62}{11} > n_1^0 > 2$	
				$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < V^3 K_c < \infty$	
12.	$CH_4 + C_2H_6 + 3NH_3 + 4O_2 + 16N_2 \leftrightarrow 3HCN + 8H_2O + 16N_2$	2		$n_1^0 + n_2^0 + n_3^0 + 5n_4^0 = n^0 = 25 \text{ mol}$	
	$n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad n_3^0 \quad n_4^0 \quad 4n_4^0$			$n_1^0 = n_2^0 = \frac{1}{3} n_3^0$	
				$\xi_{\max} = (n^0 - 19n_1^0)/16$	
				$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{25}{9} > n_1^0 > 1$	
				$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < V^2 K_c < \infty$	

ated on the straight-line AB, eqn. (29).

As the constant of equilibrium K_x increases, the initial composition of the system of reaction, that assures a maximum value of conversion, approaches to the composition corresponding to stoichiometric mixture. For low and medium values of the equilibrium constant K_x , in order to achieve a maximum conversion ξ_{\max} , the initially introduced amount of air should be less than the stoichiometric amount. It is only when $K_x \rightarrow \infty$, the optimal composition corresponds to the stoichiometric mixture. This situation appears in all oxidation reactions with air.

The coordinates of the maximum points, corresponding to various curves with $K_x = \text{constant}$ (Fig. 2), can be easily calculated by using eqns. (29) and (31). The results are presented in Table 2. One can notice that in order to achieve curves of maximum values similar to those presented in Fig. 2, K_x may have any value and the initial quantity of NO, corresponding to maximum conversion, takes different values situated in the interval $2 < n_{NO}^0 < 14/3 \text{ mol}$. These matters present practical importance in the oxidation reaction of NO with air.

A complete picture of the above-mentioned reaction may be obtained by a representation of the isoconversion curves

$K_x = \text{constant}$, as presented in Fig. 3. Particularities of these curves are already discussed³.

Table 2. Maximum conversion ξ_{\max} for various values of the equilibrium constant K_x , corresponding to the reaction (23)*

ξ_{\max}	n_{NO}^0 mol	K_x	K_c/V mol ⁻¹
0	4.67	0	0
0.055	4.52	10 ⁻²	1.41 × 10 ⁻³
0.150	4.27	10 ⁻¹	1.44 × 10 ⁻²
0.335	3.77	1	0.15
0.567	3.15	10	1.57
0.757	2.65	10 ²	15.8
0.877	2.33	10 ³	164.9
0.940	2.16	10 ⁴	1610
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
1.000	2	∞	∞

*Data presented in the last column correspond to the situation when the reaction takes place at constant T, V .

In the approximation of perfect gases, irrespective of the presence and absence of inert gas, the curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ may be calculated by using the relation,

$$\ln p(\text{atm}) = - \frac{\ln K_x}{\Delta n} - \frac{\Delta G_T^0}{\Delta nRT} \quad (32)$$

where Gibbs free energy of reaction, ΔG_T^0 at temperature T and pressure $p = 1$ atm, is obtained as follows :

$$\Delta G_T^0 = \Delta H_{298}^0 + \Delta \bar{C}_p^0 (T - 298) - T \Delta S_{298}^0 - T \Delta \bar{C}_p^0 \ln \frac{T}{298} \quad (33)$$

in which ΔH_{298}^0 and ΔS_{298}^0 represent the standard change of enthalpy and entropy corresponding to the reaction, and \bar{C}_p^0 is the average molar heat capacity at $p = 1$ atm for the temperature interval $(298-T)$.

In Fig. 3 we present the isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ for reaction (23). Calculations were made by using eqns. (32) and (33), with necessary data from tables⁴.

Fig. 3. The isoconversion curves $K_x = \text{constant}$ for the reaction (23).

According to the conditions of temperature T and pressure p in which the reaction takes place, the constant of equilibrium K_x has a particular value. By knowing the value of the constant K_x , one may calculate the optimal proportion of mixing the reactants, so that the value of conversion ξ should be maximum. The phenomenon is similar in the case of oxidation reactions with air enriched with oxygen.

If reaction (23) takes place at constant T , V , the expression of the equilibrium constant $K_c(T)$ is as follows :

$$K_c = \frac{4\xi^2 V}{(n_1^0 - 2\xi)^2 (n_2^0 - \xi)} \quad (34)$$

where initial amounts n_1^0 and n_2^0 satisfy again eqn. (24).

By applying the logarithm to eqn. (34) and then differentiating the result, with the imposed conditions that $T = \text{constant}$, $V = \text{constant}$, $K_c = \text{constant}$, $\xi = \text{maximum}$, $d\xi = 0$, we obtain, as a result, the same eqn. (26). The conclusion is that eqs. (26)–(30) remain the same even when the reaction takes place under isothermal-isochoric conditions, the conclusion that also remains valid for all oxidation reactions with air (Table 1).

The ratio K_c/V , which depends only on the temperature T and volume V corresponding to the system of reaction, presents importance for the considered reaction. For various values of the ratio K_c/V , we obtain again the curves of maximum values similar to those from Fig. 2.

The coordinates of points of maximum values are presented in Table 2. For maximum points, n_{NO}^0 takes various values within the interval, $2 < n_{\text{NO}}^0 < 14/3$ mol. In case of very high values of the ratio K_c/V , the optimal proportion of mixing the reactants is the stoichiometric one, the situation in which the reaction is practically complete. In case of low and medium values of the ratio K_c/V , the conversion would be maximum, if the amount of introduced air would be less

Table 3. Oxidation reactions with air, in gaseous phase, where nitrogen is both inert gas and a product of reaction

Sl. no.	Reaction, initial quantities of reactants n_1^0, n_2^0, \dots and expressions of the equilibrium constants K_x and K_c	Δn mol	Relations between initial quantities of reactants in order to obtain curves of maximum $\xi = f(n_1^0)$ similar to those presented in Fig. 4
1.	$4\text{NH}_3 + 3\text{O}_2 + 12\text{N}_2 \leftrightarrow 2\text{N}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O} + 12\text{N}_2$ $n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$	1	$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 19 \text{ mol}$ $\xi_{\text{max}} = \frac{(n^0 - n_1^0)(8n^0 - 10n_1^0)}{92n^0 - 17n_1^0}$ $0 < \xi_{\text{max}} < 1; \frac{76}{5} > n_1^0 > 4$
	$K_x = \frac{4 \times 6^6 \xi^6 (2n_2^0 + \xi)^2}{(n^0 + \xi)(n_1^0 - 4\xi)^4 (n_2^0 - 3\xi)^3}$ $K_c = \frac{4 \times 6^6 \xi^6 (2n_2^0 + \xi)^2}{V(n_1^0 - 4\xi)^4 (n_2^0 - 3\xi)^3}$		$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < VK_c < \infty$

Table 3 (contd.)

<p>2. $N_2H_4 + O_2 + 4N_2 \leftrightarrow N_2 + 2H_2O + 4N_2$</p> <p style="text-align: center;">$n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$</p> $K_x = \frac{4\xi^2(4n_2^0 + \xi)}{(n^0 + \xi)(n_1^0 - \xi)(n_2^0 - \xi)}$ $K_c = \frac{4\xi^2(4n_2^0 + \xi)}{V(n_1^0 - \xi)(n_2^0 - \xi)}$	1	<p>$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 6 \text{ mol}$</p> $\xi_{\max} = \frac{4(n^0 - n_1^0)^2}{15n^0 + 10n_1^0}$ <p>$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; 6 > n_1^0 > 1$</p> <p>$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < VK_c < \infty; \text{Fig. 4.}$</p>
<p>3. $4CH_3NH_2 + 9O_2 + 36N_2 \leftrightarrow 2N_2 + 4CO_2 + 10H_2O + 36N_2$</p> <p style="text-align: center;">$n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$</p> $K_x = \frac{20^{10} \xi^{14} (2n_2^0 + \xi)^2}{(n^0 + 3\xi)^3 (n_1^0 - 4\xi)^4 (n_2^0 - 9\xi)^9}$ $K_c = \frac{20^{10} \xi^{14} (2n_2^0 + \xi)^2}{V^3 (n_1^0 - 4\xi)^4 (n_2^0 - 9\xi)^9}$	3	<p>$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 49 \text{ mol}$</p> $\xi_{\max} = \frac{2(n^0 - n_1^0)(4n^0 - 11n_1^0)}{284n^0 - 59n_1^0}$ <p>$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{196}{11} > n_1^0 > 4$</p> <p>$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < V^3 K_c < \infty$</p>
<p>4. $4CH_3NO_2 + 3O_2 + 12N_2 \leftrightarrow 2N_2 + 4CO_2 + 6H_2O + 12N_2$</p> <p style="text-align: center;">$n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad 4n_2^0$</p> $K_x = \frac{4^5 6^6 \xi^{10} (2n_2^0 + \xi)^2}{(n^0 + 5\xi)^5 (n_1^0 - 4\xi)^4 (n_2^0 - 3\xi)^3}$ $K_c = \frac{4^5 6^6 \xi^{10} (2n_2^0 + \xi)^2}{V^5 (n_1^0 - 4\xi)^4 (n_2^0 - 3\xi)^3}$	5	<p>$n_1^0 + 5n_2^0 = n^0 = 19 \text{ mol}$</p> $\xi_{\max} = \frac{2(n^0 - n_1^0)(4n^0 - 5n_1^0)}{92n^0 - 17n_1^0}$ <p>$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{76}{5} > n_1^0 > 4$</p> <p>$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < V^5 K_c < \infty$</p>
<p>5. $CH_3NH_2 + CH_3NO_2 + 3O_2 + 12N_2 \leftrightarrow N_2 + 2CO_2 + 4H_2O + 12N_2$</p> <p style="text-align: center;">$n_1^0 \quad n_2^0 \quad n_3^0 \quad 4n_3^0$</p> $K_x = \frac{4^5 \xi^6 (4n_3^0 + \xi)}{(n^0 + 2\xi)^2 (n_1^0 - \xi)(n_2^0 - \xi)(n_3^0 - 3\xi)^3}$ $K_c = \frac{4^5 \xi^6 (4n_3^0 + \xi)}{V^2 (n_1^0 - \xi)(n_2^0 - \xi)(n_3^0 - 3\xi)^3}$	2	<p>$n_1^0 + n_2^0 + 4n_3^0 = n^0 = 17 \text{ mol}$ $n_1^0 = n_2^0$</p> $\xi_{\max} = \frac{4(n^0 - 2n_1^0)(n^0 - 4n_1^0)}{47n^0 - 19n_1^0}$ <p>$0 < \xi_{\max} < 1; \frac{17}{4} > n_1^0 > 1$</p> <p>$0 < K_x < \infty; 0 < V^2 K_c < \infty$</p>

than the stoichiometric quantity. These matters remain valid in case of all oxidation reactions with air that take place at constant T, V , independently of the value of Δn .

Table 1 presents the results obtained for other oxidation reactions with air, where nitrogen is only inert gas, and the maximum conversion ξ_{\max} decreases linearly with the amount of reactant n_1^0 . We indicated in the first column of the table the reaction, the initial quantities of reactants n_1^0, n_2^0, \dots and the expressions of equilibrium constants K_x and K_c , all necessary to make calculations by procedure indi-

cated in case of reaction (23). For reactions with no volume change, $\Delta n = 0$, and equilibrium constants have equal values, as follows: $K_x = K_p = K_c = K$. We indicated in the last column, the relations between the initial quantities of reactants n_1^0, n_2^0, \dots in order to obtain curves of maximum similar to those presented in Fig. 2. We also indicated the linear dependence between the maximum conversion ξ_{\max} and the amount n_1^0 of reactant. Relations remain identical for each reaction, when the reaction takes place at $T = \text{constant}, p = \text{constant}$, or at $T = \text{constant}, V = \text{constant}$. In case of reac-

Fig. 4. Equilibrium conversion ξ as a function of the initial amount ($n_{N_2H_4}^0$) for the reaction $N_2H_4 + O_2 + 4N_2 \leftrightarrow N_2 + 2H_2O + 4N_2$, at different values of the equilibrium constant K_x : (1) $K_x = 1.59 \times 10^{-2}$, (2) $K_x = 0.19$, (3) $K_x = 2.52$, (4) $K_x = 16.3$, (5) $K_x = 81.4$, (6) stoichiometric mixture and total conversion of reactants into products. The eqn. of curve CD is indicated in Table 3.

tions in which, besides O_2 and N_2 , other two or more components participate, the components should be stoichiometrically mixed in order to obtain curves of maximum similar to those presented in Fig. 2. We indicated in the table the variation limits for the maximum conversion ξ_{max} , for the amount n_1^0 of reactant that assures it and for the equilibrium constants K_x respectively K_c .

By interpreting the data presented in Table 1, we came to the same conclusions as in the case of reaction (23): (i) for all oxidation reactions with air, where nitrogen is only inert gas, maximum conversion ξ_{max} decreases linearly with

the amount of reactant n_1^0 , provided that reactions take place under isothermal-isobaric or isothermal-isochoric conditions and (ii) in case of low and medium values of the equilibrium constants, the amount of introduced air, in order to achieve maximum conversion, should be less than the stoichiometric amount. It is only for high values of the equilibrium constants ($K_x \rightarrow \infty$, $K_c \rightarrow \infty$), the amount of air assuring maximum conversion tends to the stoichiometric amount and the reaction is practically complete.

Oxidation reactions with air, where nitrogen is both inert gas and a product of reaction:

We present in Table 3 the data obtained for five oxidation reactions with air, where nitrogen is both an inert gas and a product of the reaction. Calculations were made by Lagrange's method of undetermined multipliers, as presented above. The results obtained will be interpreted in the same manner as in the case of reactions presented in Table 1, but with one difference – the value of the maximum conversion ξ_{max} decreases with the amount of reactant n_1^0 , according to the equation of a curve (Fig. 4) indicated in the last column of Table 3.

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